

Factors Affecting the Gender Pay Gap in Pakistan

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Abstract

This study discusses the factors affecting the gender pay gap in Pakistan. When we look back over the decades; we can see that there has been an increase in advanced and exploratory research on the topic of the Gender Pay Gap. Differences in the workplace and the reasons for them have piqued the public's interest. The reasons for these disparities in the workplace are significant because access to these opportunities has numerous economic, social, and psychological consequences. With the rising issues of the gender pay gap not gaining enough awareness and the injustice for women in the workplace by not getting compensated for their hard work while men continue to pocket their bumped-up salaries, it is a shame there is no policy governing women's rights in the workplace. Hence, the requirement for this study is to study the in-depth reasoning behind this problem.

Keywords: Gender, Pay gap, Public, Pakistan

Introduction

The monetary rewards one receives are typically measured by the workforce advantages one receives, but is the disparity in your salary a fair estimation when your gender is targeted with a lack of rights and opportunities to allow you to rise in the first place? The impact of non-qualification or non-work-related characteristics (e.g., your race, gender, and ethnicity) on the benefits you receive at work is beneficial to some but disadvantageous to many (Kelly & Bayes, 1988). For years, researchers have worked tirelessly to identify workplace discrimination and its causes in the United States and around the world. The studies have mostly focused on a single type of discrimination that accounts for the gender pay gap, access to advancement, and access to commanding positions. Few studies have taken on the task of conducting a meta-analysis of previous studies that estimate the impact of gender-based discrimination on women in the workplace. A few have attempted extensive research (see Jarrell & Stanley, 2004; Stanley & Jarrell, 1998; Weichselbaumer & Winter-Ebmer, 2005), but no conclusive statement has been derived as a result of a lack of systematic review of the existing literature and sources.

Men have the space to put themselves in places where they can get their hands dirty and challenge themselves outside the confines of societal norms set for women, which directly contributes to the gender pay gap. Males have an advantage over women in terms of earning a higher wage/salary due to their willingness to strive and reach for such jobs. Another factor that contributes to this is Pakistan's patriarchal society and its hold on the country's ever-growing youth (Tunio, Jariko, Børsen, Shaikh, Mushtaque, & Brahmi, 2021).

According to Oelz, Olney, and Tomei (2013), it is common knowledge that many male-dominated organizations and households prioritize gender over merit. Cultural and social norms in a country based on the family system have a significant impact on a woman's life, forcing her to succumb to societal pressures and rendering a resource for the country dormant. Due to patriarchal dominance, 45 percent of our workforce is idle. A male-dominated society with sugar-coated benefits for women allows men to make decisions based solely on their preferences. Unlike women, who must choose between having a family and having a successful career like

a man at the expense of necessities? So much so that even employers have not shown much financial or other support (Lewis & Price, 1988).

Task Selection

With the growing demand for human resources in different industries, various societal norms have shadowed how people opt for jobs and tasks. If we divide the supply of human resources into males and females, a certain pattern can be observed where specific tasks are preferred by men and the others by women (Miller & Vagins, 2018). This has to do with physical limitations, societal pressures, and an overall psychological impact that has forced employees and employers to develop an unconscious bias when hiring or assigning tasks. For instance, it is observed that men take odd jobs and at odd hours more conveniently than women. This may have multiple external factors such as ease of commuting, family engagements, etc. This may have impacted some individuals who would argue that the gender pay gap prevails across the professional world, however, the fact that men and women have different preferences when it comes to task or job selection cannot be ignored. It is also observed that since men are physically stronger most jobs with physical endurance are filled by men, the construction industry for instance is predominantly led by men. On the other hand, works on creativity are mainly led by women such as soft interiors, architecture, etc. (Miller & Vagins, 2018).

Salary Negotiation

As a rule of thumb and due to prevailing norms, women have always been underappreciated when being compensated for their work. This mainly has to do with women not being as aware as men working within the industry; employers exploit this lack of awareness and pay women less than compared to a man for the same job. This has made it difficult for working women to maneuver within the workspace and excel (Blau & Kahn, 2006).

According to Nguyen-Huu (2021), it is also the reason many women find it difficult as compared to a man to reach positions of influence and authority. Employers often argue that in patriarchal societies such as Pakistan, men often lead the household bearing all expenses of dependent members of the family and so a relatively higher compensation is justified. Gender differences, both in entering negotiations and when negotiating, have been proved to exist: Men are usually more likely to enter into negotiation than women and when negotiating they obtain better deals than women.

These gender differences help to explain the gender gap in wages, as starting salaries and wage increases or promotions throughout an individual's career are often the results of bilateral negotiations. Thirty-six percent of men always negotiate their starting salaries following a job offer, as opposed to only 26 percent of women. So why aren't women negotiating for the job salaries they want and deserve? Well, 19 percent claim that asking for more money is just plain uncomfortable (Blau & Kahn, 2006).

According to Kaya (2021), lacking the confidence (15 percent) or negotiating skills (15 percent) in order to successfully request a raise factored into their decision as well. Only 11 percent of those surveyed claim that they were satisfied with the original starting salary offered to them. It's also interesting to note how men and women view salary negotiations. Women, on the other hand, view the process as being "similar to going to the dentist." That might explain why 55 percent of women are anxious before heading in to negotiate salary, while only 39 percent of men are.

Another factor in determining the stress level that comes with salary negotiations is who your boss is. Interestingly, female employees would prefer to ask a male boss for a raise (28 percent), and only 11 percent would want to ask a female boss. For 74 percent of men, it didn't matter if the boss was a male or female. Negotiating for a higher salary (or a raise) can be a stressful or successful experience. It's really all in how you view it. Know your worth and negotiate confidently to get the salary and rise that you truly deserve (Kay & Shipman, 2014).

Breaking the Barrier - Slow Growth of Society Into Modernism

"In spite of the fact that ladies' cooperation in advanced education and in the work market has expanded notably in the industrialized nations (Chao & Rones, 2007), there are as yet striking distinctions in sexual orientation in vocation achievement (Eagly & Carli, 2007). Two generally utilized marks of profession achievement are advancements and compensation (Seibert, Crant, & Kraimer, 1999), with the exact information showing bigger distinctions in sexual orientation in compensation. In their meta-examination of profession indicators, Ng, Eby, Sorensen, and Feldman (2005) found bigger generally speaking impact sizes for the distinctions in sexual orientation in compensation ($r = .18$) than in advancements ($r = .08$). Ladies' support in medication has expanded emphatically in the last many years. In the United States, the extent of ladies' clinical understudies expanded from 6% to 49% from 1960 to 2004 (Jagsi et al., 2006). German measurements from 2008 mirrored that 61% of generally clinical understudies were female (destatis, 2009) and that ladies represented 41% of utilized doctors (Bundesärztekammer, 2009). As in other word related fields, nonetheless, ladies are still underrepresented in higher situations in medication (Reed & Buddeberg-Fischer, 2001) and have lower levels of vocation accomplishment than their male partners (Buddeberg-Fischer, Stamm, Buddeberg, & Klaghofer, 2008). Female doctors procure not exactly their male partners in both the United States (Bashaw and Heywood, 2001) and Germany, where in 2006 female doctors in regular work acquired 24% not exactly male doctors similarly situated (destatis, 2008). Customary orientation jobs are viewed as basic in making sense of the orientation hole in vocation achievement (Betz & Fitzgerald, 1987; Eagly & Karau, 1991). Orientation jobs not just characterize reciprocal obligations of ladies and men in family and in the public eye, yet additionally determine character qualities that are socially expected and esteemed in ladies and men (Deaux & LaFrance, 1998; Eagly, 2000). The male orientation job should be visible as useful to an expert vocation for something like two reasons. In the first place, the assignment of youngster rising and family obligations essentially to ladies makes it more straightforward for men to keep chasing after their vocations, in any event, when they become fathers. Second, the character qualities that are gainful to an expert profession are practically indistinguishable from those that are vital to the male orientation job (Betz & Fitzgerald, 1987; Eagly & Karau, 2002). Koenig, Eagly, Mitchell, and Ristikari (2011) displayed in their meta-examination of 68 investigations that individuals saw pioneers as more like men than to ladies, more agentic than common, and more manly than ladylike. Prior to illustrating the objectives of our review, we momentarily talk about the job of vocation interference and manly (agentic) character attributes for professional achievement."

The above article plainly states how people with similar instructive foundations and assets are as yet confronting a distinction by the way they are paid for their administrations. This out decides the way that ladies are paid less because of somewhat less capabilities. Two specialists or specialists with a similar instructive foundation are paid distinctively founded on their sexes. This has more to do with the mental speculations that exist and impact the compensation scale. It is many times contended that the life as a parent punishment denies ladies of colossally huge vocation years, which ultimately is reflected in their compensations.

Age and Earnings

The relation of age plays a majorly complex role in the ever-large problem of the gender pay gap. It is on record that women working in organizations already face a disadvantage of being paid fewer salaries than men just based on their gender alone. When you throw in the factor of age, it is now a problem on a larger scale, as it is recorded that women aged 40-49 face the largest pay gap (Bobilev, Boschini, & Roine, 2020).

According to Segovia-Pérez, Castro Núñez, Santero Sánchez, and Laguna Sánchez (2020), men are paid 24.5% more at the same age. There are several reasons contributing to this that is unspoken of – especially due to the fact that they are nonsensical. One of the industries in which this is the most apparent and continues to grow is the Media Industry. In the world of showbiz, males and females play big roles that should be getting paid equal wages but instead, actresses are paid millions less than actors. These are roles that were previously dominated by men but since the growing awareness about this topic, women are now earning 83 cents for every man who earns a dollar. In professional and related jobs, women are more likely than men to be employed, according to 2019 BLS data. But in the professional world, there are many fewer women than men who hold higher-paying positions (Baum, 2013).

The average gross hourly salary difference between males and females at age 30 is nine percent, but by the age of fifty, the difference has tripled to twenty-eight percent. Women frequently transition to part-time employment at age 30 in order to care for children, whereas males typically increase their working hours at the same age (Busch & Holst, 2009).

The average income for women between the ages of 30 and 50 remains essentially unchanged due to the fact that part-time work is typically paid less per hour and part-timers are less likely to occupy leadership positions (Bobilev, Boschini, & Roine, 2020).

According to Busch, & Holst, (2009), women may be less able to put in the long hours necessary for a large promotion at their employment or to participate in networking and job search activities that promote financially beneficial job transfers, due to family and caregiving duties. Younger females are slowly breaking the barrier of the pay gap in their age group as they are more motivated to complete higher education and certifications that land them job roles in higher positions.

These effects may be exacerbated if employers believe that women are less likely to stay in the labor force in the long run, or if women are less likely to seek promotions and raise within and across firms in anticipation of needing more time flexibility or due to family location decisions in which the primary earner's career, usually the husband's, takes precedence. Younger females are slowly breaking the barrier of the pay gap in their age group as they are more motivated to complete higher education and certifications that land them job roles in higher positions (Kaya, 2021).

Parenthood

According to Landmesser (2019, September), fathers are rewarded more than childless men, but mothers are penalized more than childless women. Even while the gender difference for childless employees has narrowed over time, the parenting penalty stays consistent after adjusting for a range of characteristics such as education and experience. We illustrate how the gender gap, parenting penalties, and fatherhood benefits vary among affluent nations. Furthermore, we highlight how maternity breaks, paternity leaves, parental leaves, and publicly sponsored child care might help alleviate these inequities by assisting parents—both men and women—in engaging in employment and caring. Finally, we propose that policy should address pay disparity not only by gender but also by parenting. The guy may work harder and longer, but the woman may work less owing to her involvement in caregiving tasks outside the workplace.

According to research, time spent on "feminine" domestic duties such as food preparation and housekeeping affects pay for both men and women. On average, women perform more of these duties. Well-designed research based on survey data may also call into question the specialization argument. One research compares paired and single men and women, both childless and parents, and contends that if specialization explains income inequalities, both partnered women and moms, would face penalties. However, males earn more when their partners work less than full-time, but women do not (Kidd & Michael, 1993.)

Role of Part-Time Jobs

Keeping up with the context of this particular research, we can make sure that the environment or the society is dependent on part-time jobs, as part-time jobs are the key indicators and source of self-growth for especially young individuals going through their academic qualification phases. Part-time jobs can be very specific and very assistive sources of income for individuals in regard to being supportive to their basic daily routine needs and even academic purposes (Côté & Allahar, 1996).

With the costs standing out and arriving at the apogee, Pakistan becomes one of those nations where the concurrent acquisition of academics of at least two young individuals can leave the family helpless. Guardians of the understudies are left with practically zero choices to meet the uses, which turn out to be truly tiresome for the family to make due, particularly in the ages of cost climbing and inflation. To defeat this pressure, the guardians suffocate into the steadily heaping obligation, consume their time on earth for profit, or sell their resources, with the high any desire for recovering the cash with their child's future employment (Costa, Joyce, & Parodi, 2020). According to Côté and Allahar (1996), different nations require a job inversion when young

individuals land for part-jobs to meet the costs and to pay for their schooling. Fully intent on making understudies constant of the freeways of life, this pattern can allow guardians to hurl a euphoric moan of help. Working part-time can assist with sharing the weight, rather a heavy one that is constantly flung on the guardians in Pakistan. In any case, this pattern is viewed as a weird case and still can't seem to cause disturbances in our country.

We have spoken about the importance and significance of Part-Time jobs within society, and we have also briefly stated the requirement and its need in such times of inflation and crisis, the main motive is to discuss the equal opportunities of Part-Time jobs for Women as of the opposite gender (Anderson, Forth, Metcalf, & Kirby, 2001).

According to Boris (2019), women in Pakistan don't reserve the privilege of the same working hours as that of men, they are banned from working in numerous businesses, and there are no regulations or sacred arrangements commanding equivalent compensation for equivalent work. Besides, there are no regulations in Pakistan ordering non-segregation in employing rehearsals based on gender. Indeed, even in workplaces, where accomplished women in all actuality do land positions, their conjugal status matters. It is unlawful in evolved economies to get some information about conjugal status during a job interview.

In Pakistan, such inquiries are a standard, and women with no family strings are liked over additionally accomplished up-and-comers. Representatives with minor kids have no extra rights to adaptable or temporary plans for getting work done. Indeed, even the installments made by working moms for childcare are not tax-exempt. Worldwide, women address 49.6 percent of the complete populace, yet they comprise just 40.8 percent of the absolute labor force in the proper area. Contrasts in the manner people are treated under the law may, to some extent, make sense of this gap (Clift & Brazaitis, 2000). According to Clift & Brazaitis (2000), his gap in Pakistan is exceptionally high. Just a little north of 20% of the useful age women is financially dynamic. Fruitful woman business visionaries of Pakistan concede that the victimization of their gender is still high, but things are improving with time. Some think that it is worthwhile, as being female business visionaries their partners in a similar business broaden full collaboration and help. Be that as it may, the majority of the women in Pakistan works casually and is mercilessly taken advantage of.

In man-centric social orders as in a large portion of Pakistan, men apply a lot of impact over the existence of their female family members and quite often have selective command over family pay. Alternately, men hesitant to see women in the workplace can crash progress toward more noteworthy cooperation of women in the workforce. Unbendable as it might sound, this view has been emphasized in resulting subjective meetings by metropolitan women who are keen on working yet are discouraged by male relatives due to their misperception of current workplaces. If we speak internationally, especially about the Western Nations, Gender contrasts in paid and neglected time at work are a significant part of gender disparity (Morgan, 2011).

According to Morgan (2011), policy press women will generally invest more energy in neglected family and family care work, and men invest additional time in paid work. This inconsistent dissemination of time makes boundaries to women's progression in working and diminishes women's monetary security. Resulting in crisis and much more disputes related to gender inequality. More women are getting advanced education in Pakistan than in earlier many years, however working women keep on confronting troublesome difficulties, especially in satisfying double liabilities at work and home — and getting to childcare. In view of information from the International Labor Organization for women matured 15-64, ongoing World Bank measurements plot growth in general female cooperation in the Pakistani workforce from a little more than 12% in 1995 to over an expected 26 percent in 2018 (Anderson, Forth, Metcalf, & Kirby, 2001). Notwithstanding this slow shift, female workforce cooperation in Pakistan is still low in correlation with other agricultural nations in Asia, like Nepal, Bangladesh, and the Philippines. Indeed, even among profoundly taught women, there are somewhat not many that work outside the home: as per a short distributed in 2016 by the Asian Development Bank, something like 25% of Pakistani women with college-level training accomplishes paid work outside the home. (Fortin, 2006).

Education for women is progressively empowered, yet there doesn't appear to be a comparing acknowledgment of women's constant jobs inside the family as nurturers and professions, and the extra weight that puts on women when they occupy temporary jobs. Women, regardless of whether working external of the home —

remain fundamentally answerable for raising youngsters and satisfying the assignments of cooking, taking care of, being mindful, and cleaning that make life reasonable for other relatives. This is the vital reason, male dominance in job sector and even within the part-time jobs sector remains stabilized and in the favor of the male gender (Rosenfeld, Trappe, & Gornick, 2004).

Gender-Based Discrimination

By and by just 10% of women have post-optional training while their possibilities working for pay increment three-overlay with present auxiliary schooling contrasted on women and essential instruction. More trained ladies also will undoubtedly land better quality positions. Pakistan is a man-centric culture where men are the fundamental power figures and ladies are subordinate. This has serious repercussions on ladies' and men's life prospects (Bobbitt-Zeher, 2007).

If we speak about how the market actually works, there is no concept of a market, there is a concept of a society. As per the public, in Pakistan as well as in Western nations, men are the essential dynamic experts in the family. Therefore, the importance and male dominance initiate from the societal point of view, spreading towards various sectors, out of which the 'market' or job sector is one of them (Patterson & Benuyenah, 2021). Introductory discoveries of a review show that around a fourth of senior residents, or around 25%, battle with regular essential requirements for medical attention and supplements. Ladies charge more terrible than men in such a manner. Around 24% of additional laid-out ladies fight in getting to fundamental necessities like food and refuge. This is one point, in regard to the expert climate and a developing proficient association, on a normal a female mistaken as a Senior Executive or a senior profile after her 10 years of experience on average, in comparison of 5 years of a male employee. Women in numerous nations on normal have time-based compensations way beneath those of their male partners. These remuneration qualifications change as extensively as 10 - 40 percent, differentiating and averaging the whole working people split by orientation. Officially, these distinctions are represented. All things considered, ladies give off an impression of being short of time to get (significantly) more. They frequently have a bigger number of tasks to take care of than simply work for cash, on the off chance that one includes homegrown obligations (Patterson & Benuyenah, 2021).

What's more, they are once in a while sexually harassed by men, with vocation results including passing on a task because of the pressure of this. There are many purposes behind the different professional decisions that women make. Regardless, a wide range of individuals ponders these changing choices exceptionally regularly. In a couple of callings in certain nations, it happens that women procure more than their male partners. These women, generally speaking, have something similar or better instruction, work all day, and have had the option to arrange their compensations. This particular accomplishment leads the opposite gender to be felt threatened as the society sets an example for the male to be the dominant and more superior being as compared to the female, viewing such accomplishments would make the opposite gender curious and insecure (Patterson & Benuyenah, 2021).

The gender wage gap in Pakistan exists because of the customary designs set up, however with the support of the neighborhood and worldwide philanthropies, there are new courses of action and resources to execute them effectively. Women presently make up fewer than 18% of STEM experts in Pakistan. One can credit this gap to the education pace of women and the cultural tension for women to seek after a more female-overwhelmed field (Johns & Merida, 2013).

The proficiency rate for women is 47% in contrast with 71% for men, which further fuels the gender wage gap in Pakistan. The pace of workplace badgering just adds to the powerlessness of bosses to address the issues of instructed and qualified women, and dissuades women from adding to STEM fields. The gender wage gap exists across a huge number of countries, areas, and callings, proportionally influencing low-pay women. Pakistan is the focal point of this imbalance. As per the Global Wage Report 2018/19 (ILO), women in Pakistan acquire 34% not as much as men by and large. A similar report likewise found women in Pakistan comprise 90% of the base 1% of breadwinners in the country. Women universally are moving into a developing space as pioneers, entrepreneurs, startup organizers, geeks, businesswomen, as well as locally situated specialists. From their current jobs in conventional financial areas of agribusiness, wellbeing, training, and so forth, women are

presently making advances in the Fourth Industrial Revolution to drive worldwide and territorial information economies of scale. Imbalance in a potential open door and in working Pakistan's hindrances against women's financial strengthening by and large incorporate absence of gender-delicate strategies, pay disparity, mentalities/provocation at workplaces, and generalizations characterizing women's job in the public eye (Johns & Merida,2013).

For those previously venturing into the labor force, notwithstanding, extra obstructions incorporate an absence of gendered foundation at workplaces, gender pay gaps, restricted portability, shortage of public latrines, disavowal/segregation of expert turn of events and initiative open doors, employer stability, and other word-related perils. For Women's Economics to turn into a reality in Pakistan, both customary and arising word-related hindrances should be fundamentally and foundationally tended to (Johns & Merida,2013).

Cultural Norms & Glass Ceiling

Pakistan stands as the third-worst in the world in gender equality, according to the WEF. The gender gap in Pakistan has been damaged with time despite financial growth. In a review, experimenters believed that men pushed for higher compensations in scenarios where the hiring manager was a woman (Patterson& Walcutt, 2013).

And Society plays the biggest role in this case when it comes to women, men often feel threatened by “Women Bosses, CEOs “ who try or have accomplished their desired goal in the realm. Pakistan is filled with a glass ceiling situation for women, as researchers believe Pakistan is the third-worst country when it comes to the gender pay gap or any equality for women. There's an invisible barrier for women that are in evolution and working with men. Most men just can't be compared to women - they always want more compensation - and feel threatened if smart women have more power over them. Due to social class, degree, or cultural issues, women face a glass ceiling, and most of them don't even know about it but go through it (Gatto, 2020).

Women living in rural areas of Pakistan are most likely to face more difficult times compared to a woman living in cities. Most of the time social and cultural rules only apply to women and not men most of the time women suffer so much when it comes to getting a degree they always wanted, or a dream job they have been waiting to work for. Women tend to go through so much due to the glass ceiling and men indicating women shouldn't get more compensation than him at a certain company (Gatto, 2020).

The Gender Gap in Pakistan has crumbled with time despite financial advancement. The study predicts that AI (Artificial Intelligence) undoubtedly many trends are moving in the right direction for women. It can be that the next wave of technology might change the circumstances for Women in the future - the glass ceiling and cultural criteria should be put aside and let them accomplish their vision (Costa Dias, Joyce, & Parodi, 2020).

Psychological conflicts between men and women could account for up to 15% of the pay gap.

Male supremacy in Pakistani society has worsened the condition of women - prohibiting their access to higher levels of the institution. In This Islamic State Of Pakistan, most women are nurtured in public or management sciences, their occupational choice is academia or office desk jobs. Due to being a male-dominated nation - half of the women are extremely talented and filled with skills, and some of them can be better CEOs, Directors, they should get a higher workplace appreciation, but women are kept thwarted by offering fewer incentives as correlated to the male staff of the same team (Olsen & Walby, 2004).

Also, the worst thing happening around due to this brutal society is that 30 to 45% of the women tend to do a BA or Diploma Certificates, only completing college, due to not getting an opportunity in their desired field. The uncertainty of opposition in the leadership field is particularly associated with gender and is so huge that they are bound to make a choice, which they hardly relish. For most women, the family takes importance in overall consequences. Thus, the job takes a lesser place in her life. On the contrary, it is generally seen that her male colleague is benefited in every aspect so that he can work well. This fortifies the glass ceiling (Bobbitt-Zeher, 2007).

Conclusion

The focus of this research is to look into the factors that lead to the gender pay gap and its prevailing rise in organizations across Pakistan, given the continued backlash. Women have been subjected to pay discrimination at a higher rate than men, even when they are more competent. We look to be approaching a moment of pessimism about the ongoing gender revolution's future. We've arrived at a fork in the road where two very different ideas collide. Possible futures appear in front of us, an "optimistic scenario," based on the assumption that gender inequalities will continue to decrease, despite the fact that they are still significant. We consider current institutional structures to be in a state of equilibrium. The optimistic outlook is based on the simple notion that the forces that shape our world are in our favor. Changes during the last half-century are still in play, and they will bring about further change in the future. There has been a significant decrease in gender inequality.

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